

THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGY "TALKING WALL" FOR THE PURPOSE OF PATRIOTIC EDUCATION OF CHILDREN OF SENIOR PRESCHOOL AGE

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Annotation: At the present stage of development of society, patriotic education is becoming one of the priority areas in the activities of preschool educational institutions. This article is devoted to this issue.

Keywords: innovative society; technology; subject-developing environment; integration; motivation; creative activity; independence.

INTRODUCTION

The educational standard of preschool education sets goals for patriotic education: creating conditions for the formation of the foundations of the patriotic consciousness of children, the possibility of positive socialization of the child, his comprehensive personal, moral, moral and cognitive development, the development of initiative and creative abilities, on the basis of types corresponding to preschool age activities.

An adult is called upon to provide a wealth of subject-developing environment in order to maximize independent children's activity.

A properly organized subject-developing environment in a group provides each child with equal opportunities for all-round development. One of the elements of the subject-developing environment is the "Talking Wall" technology, which I use in my work to achieve a certain result in the moral and patriotic education of my pupils [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Our "Talking (patriotic) wall" creates an atmosphere of emotional comfort; creates conditions for the manifestation of cognitive activity (the desire for independent activity); creates conditions for creative self-expression (children's creativity as one of the most effective forms of children's artistic development of the surrounding reality, during which they depict objects and phenomena); develops independence, fine motor skills, initiative in choosing the content of activities, visual aids; develops the communication skills of children (children comprehend the world and its laws to a large extent through communication with the adults around them: this is a well-delivered speech, a coherent expression of thoughts and feelings, understanding of non-verbal signals, initial teamwork skills, and much more); creates favorable conditions for perception and contemplation, draws children to the beauty of nature [2].

Its essence lies in the fact that the child, receiving the necessary information, has the right to choose to plan his activities and constructively use the information resource.

The "Talking Wall" technology includes developing, interactive, sensory walls in the subject-developing environment of the group.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The introduction of new technologies in the educational process of preschool institutions contributes to a more effective perception of a child who seeks to be creative in solving various life situations and wants to gain new knowledge about the world around him. The use of such technologies certainly affects the formation of positive motivation for further learning.

Children in the course of working at the "Talking (patriotic) wall" learn to express their attitude to their homeland, family, city, native nature; comment on their statements and actions, control their behavior, follow the established rules.

Children themselves update the presented material based on their interests, modify it depending on the learning situation [3].

"Talking Wall" is a unique tool that allows you to change the subject-developing environment of the group in a completely unusual way, a kind of live screen.

"Children are always willing to do something. This is very useful, and then not only should this not be interfered with, but measures must be taken to ensure that they always have something to do.

Y.Komensky.

"Talking Wall" is a tool that allows you to change the developing object-spatial environment of a preschool institution in an unusual way, a kind of live screen. The child, receiving the necessary information, independently chooses and plans his activities and constructively uses the information resource.

"Talking Wall" can integrate several educational centers:

- social and communicative center;
- center of cognitive development;

- the center of artistic and aesthetic development. The main goal and objectives of the "Talking Wall"

Purpose: creation of conditions for the full development of preschoolers in all educational areas of the Federal State Educational Standard in accordance with the specific features and requirements of the educational program of the kindergarten.

Tasks [4]:

- create an atmosphere of emotional comfort in the group.
- create conditions for the creative self-expression of the child.
- create conditions for the manifestation of cognitive activity of children.

On the wall in the group room there are magnetic strips, carpets, fishing lines, clothespins, pockets, TCO, didactic games, game chips, thematic pictures.

For the "talking wall", we select the material in accordance with the group's calendar plan, taking into account the time of year and the theme of the week.

CONCLUSION

In the process of introducing this technology, the children develop cognitive abilities and creative thinking, self-esteem has increased, they learn to independently extract information and apply it in practice. We noticed that every child began to strive for active work, and a positive creative result is visible.

We have implemented the main task - the creative activity of children, independence in choosing methods of action in various situations, has become more active.

After all, we educators, in unity with parents, want to release into the life of a child who is inquisitive and active, diversified and creatively free. Only such a person can become successful in life.

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